

5.2 REST API Web servis

Omogućava spoljnim aplikacijama (*third-party*) da čitaju podatke o aukciji, postavljaju ponude i preuzimaju rezultate. Dijagram sekvence je dat na sledećoj slici.

Slika 5 Sekvencijalni dijagram

OPTIMIZATION MODULE AND AUCTION MECHANISM OF THE APPLICATION FOR TRADE OF GUARANTEES OF ORIGIN

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Abstract - This paper presents the work of the optimization module of the Guaranties of Origin application as well as the auction mechanism itself. First, a brief overview of the entire application and its business process, as well as the software architecture, is given. Then, a description of algorithms is given, ie a mathematical model of the optimization process. The following is a functional description of the optimization module software and the auction process itself, as well as a description of the software technologies used. The application interface is shown below. Finally, a brief overview of the further development plan is given.

The optimization module was developed using the C ++ programming language on the Linux platform (specifically Oracle Linux 7.9). The basic optimization problem comes down to the problem of linear programming and open source libraries are used to solve this problem, specifically the GLU (Gnu Linear Programming Toolkit). Data on auctions, participants and other data are stored in a relational MySQL database.

The described module was developed within the HORIZON 2020 TRINITY project (H2020-863874 Transmission system enhancement of regional borders by means of Intelligent market technology).

Keywords — Guarantees of Origin-Optimization-GLPK-Linear Programming-TRINITY